

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R5.4 Report and Dataset: Geochemistry of Reservoir Rocks and Caprocks

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1 INTRODUCTION

The main purpose of this report is to provide knowledge about composition and properties of reservoir rocks and caprock. The results will be used to better constrain geomechanical investigations (WP4), dynamic modelling (WP3) and risk assessment (WP6) of the Zar-3 storage site. In summary, the WP5 activities will contribute to the project with predictive estimation on how the rocks will expect or resist the carbon dioxide storage. The work in WP5 was performed by CGS in close cooperation with VSB, NORCE and MND. The petroleum geology of the region is described by Krejčí et al (1996), Kostelníček et al. (2006) and Pícha et al. (2006).

2 SAMPLES

Core samples were provided by MND from the core repository together with the MudLogs and wireline logs, which made it possible to estimate the depth interval represented by the core samples. In addition, cutting samples were provided by MND from the ZA3 well, which cover almost entire lithological vertical profile. Sample list of the reservoirs and caprocks are in the Attachment 1 with measured (MD) and true vertical sub-sea depth (TVDSS m) of the samples, lithology, stratigraphic age, lithostratigraphy and further details.

Cores were cut in half so that backup material was preserved in MND. Selected pieces of rocks were divided into slabs, which were vacuum-impregnated with blue epoxy resin. Polished thin sections were prepared. Mineralogy, pore space and pore throats were described using optical and electron microscopy. Fluorescence light microscopy made it possible to indicate the presence of hydrocarbon micro-fluid inclusions. The position of the core samples are in Fig. 2-1.

Fig. 2-1: Core and new cutting samples for geochemical analyses. Žarošice (ZA) well numbers are shown next to each well trajectory.

Each sample documentation includes well number, initial core depth in m, core number, box number, position within the box in cm and a high resolution picture (Fig. 2-2).

Fig. 2-2: Core samples in the MND repository with well name, number, core (jádرو) number, box (vz.) number, and position within the box in cm: Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb. (ZA4A_1866 m_c1_b5) and Lower Carboniferous of the Myslejovice Fm. (ZA3_1886 m_c6_b4).

Samples collected from the repository were photo documented to show details of the rock fabric, heterogeneity and structural features, such as fractures or deformation (Fig. 2-3). All photos are stored in the project repository.

Fig. 2-3: Macro-photo of a core sample taken for chemical and petrological analyses: Zar4-1862m-core1-box6-80-90cm, Paleogene, Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb.

3 METODOLOGY

Elemental composition of total organic carbon (TOC), total inorganic carbon (TIC) and total sulfur (TS) were analysed using ELTRA 2000 instrument with three infrared detectors. TIC was measured using phosphoric acid treatment, TOC and TS by oxidation in oxygen flow at 1420 °C after carbonates removal by HCl at 40°C. TIC was recalculated to calcite or dolomite content stoichiometrically. Elemental oxide concentration for bulk rock was determined by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry.

Mineral composition was analysed using powder X-ray diffraction method with CuK α irradiation. Clay mineral grain size fraction was separated by centrifuge and oriented mounts were analysed, the diffractograms were evaluated using Sybilla software.

Optical microscopy in plane polarized light (PPL), cross-polarized light (XPL) and in fluorescent light using Leitz Leitz Orthoplan microscope MPV-II with Ploemopak fluorescence module was used with blue-violet excitation light of 400 nm wavelength, dichromatic mirror 510 nm to remove the low wavelength light, and finally a 510 nm barrier filter to remove the excitation light from the outgoing light. The microscope was equipped with a XBO 450 xenon lamp. Thin sections were further scanned by optical NIKON scanner and 2 x 3 cm sample pictures were produced.

For **electron microscopy** thin sections were coated by carbon. The electron microprobe Cameca SX100 at Masaryk University in Brno, was operated under following conditions: wavelength dispersive spectroscopy (WDS) mode, accelerating voltage 15 keV, beam current 8 nA (10 nA for silicates), spot size 8 μ m (5 μ m for silicates), analyst J. Haifler. Natural and synthetic standards and their spectral lines were used. To study chemical variations in zonal carbonate crystals, analytical points were placed in lines approx. 10 μ m apart. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was used for identification of mineral phases that did not require precise chemical analysis. Images of studied areas were recorded in back scattered electrons (BSE). The chemical formulae of carbonates were normalized to sum of cations equal 2 (or 1 in case of calcite).

Soluble organic matter was extracted from rocks using Dionex accelerated extractor by DCM – methanol mixture (97 + 3) and the solution volume was reduced by Turbovap. Elemental sulfur was removed by activated copper. Saturated (SAT), aromatic (ARO) and polar (NSO) fractions were separated on silica column. SAT and ARO fractions were analysed by gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (Agilent 7890A and 5973N MSD). Mass chromatograms were evaluated as peak areas and molecular **biomarkers** ratios calculated using three NIGOGA standards / reference samples purchased from the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate.

4 RESULTS

The characteristics of rocks, which build the planned storage site include:

- 1 - Chemical composition of rocks
- 2 - Mineralogy
- 3 - Clay minerals composition in clay grain size fraction of the rocks
- 4 - Microscopy and petrography of rocks, optical porosity
- 5 - Electron microscopy and microprobe geochemistry at a grain size of rocks
- 6 - Biomarker composition.

Results mentioned above are intended to be further used in the evaluation of petrophysical properties, e.g. permeability, of rocks and for the dynamic modelling of CO₂ storage with modelling of fluid rock interactions and thermal disequilibria after the CO₂ injection. The results are stored in project geodatabase (result R1.3).

4.1 Elemental analysis

Total 45 cores and 121 cuttings samples were analysed for total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS), the results are in Tab. 4-1 and 4-2. Calcite or dolomite content (in case of the Vranovice Fm.) were recalculated based on stoichiometry from TIC. Stratigraphy: Nes – Nesvačilka Fm., M. Paleogene, Mik – Mikulov Fm., U. Jurassic, Vran – Vranovice Fm., U. Jurassic, Nik – Nikolčice Fm., M. Jurassic, Mys – Myslejovice Fm., L. Carboniferous.

Table 4-1a. Calcite or dolomite content (Cal, Dol), total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in core samples from Žarošice (ZA) and Uhřice (UH) wells

No.	Sample Name (well_MD_C_B_from_to)	Depth m TVDSS	Strati- graphy	Calc, Dol (% _m)	TIC (% _m)	TOC (% _m)	TS (% _m)
1	ZA1_1700_22_4_45_55	1478	Nes	37.65	4.90	1.62	1.15
2	ZA1_1740_24_5_60_70	1519	Nes	21.36	2.78	1.65	1.73
3	ZA3_1460_1_1_35_45	1238	Nes	44.95	5.85	0.03	0.31
4	ZA3_1460_1_3_95_97	1240	Nes	33.65	4.38	0.54	0.31
5	ZA3_1460_1_4_67_73	1241	Nes	1.61	0.21	2.49	2.1
6	ZA3_1460_1_5_60_75	1242	Nes	0.00	0.00	4.34	2.72
7	ZA3_1465,5_2_1_45_48	1243	Nes	0.00	0.00	3.12	1.64
8	ZA3_1465,5_2_7_20_30	1249	Nes	47.56	6.19	5.92	0.83
9	ZA4_1862_1_5_51_72	1573	Nes	16.06	2.09	1.92	1.65
10	ZA4_1862_1_6_80_90	1575	Nes	10.06	1.31	6.20	1.86
11	UH-3_1707_3a_3_30_40	1418	Mik	59.93	7.80	1.00	0.38
12	UH-3_1707_3a_3_55_65	1418	Mik	64.77	8.43	0.83	0.22
13	UH-3_1707_3a_3_60_70	1418	Mik	62.39	8.12	0.85	0.28

Table 4-1b cont. Calcite or dolomite content (Cal, Dol), total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in core samples from Žarošice (ZA) and Uhřice (UH) wells

No.	Sample Name (well_MD_C_B_from_to)	Depth m TVDSS	Strati- graphy	Calc, Dol (% _m)	TIC (% _m)	TOC (% _m)	TS (% _m)
14	UH-3_1973_7_2_90_95	1683	Vran	97.34	12.67	0.13	<0.05
15	ZA5H_2093_1_1_5_15	1467	Vran	85.59	11.14	0.10	0.31
16	ZA5H_2093_1_3_45_55	1468	Vran	86.43	11.25	0.10	<0.05
17	ZA3_1595,5_3_4_51_61	1376	Vran	93.73	12.20	0.00	<0.05
18	ZA3_1595,5_3_4_80_90	1376	Vran	93.58	12.18	0.00	<0.05
19	ZA3_1701_4_2_85_95	1480	Vran	94.50	12.30	0.00	<0.05
20	ZA3_1785_5_1_60_70	1562	Vran	94.73	12.33	0.42	<0.05
21	ZA4A_1759_1_3_15_25	1503	Vran	92.81	12.08	0.70	<0.05
22	ZA4A_1778_2_4_35_45	1523	Vran	93.35	12.15	0.02	<0.05
23	ZA4A_1778_2_8_45_55	1527	Vran	95.96	12.49	0.10	<0.05
24	ZA4A_1778_2_8_50_55	1527	Vran	96.19	12.52	0.16	<0.05
25	ZA4A_1787_3_1_20_30	1529	Vran	94.58	12.31	0.00	<0.05
26	ZA4A_1787_3_3_25_30	1531	Vran	94.89	12.35	0.55	<0.05
27	ZA4A_1787_3_8_45_55	1536	Vran	94.50	12.30	0.03	<0.05
28	ZA6A_1929_1_3_80_90	1565	Vran	90.81	11.82	0.65	0.10
29	ZA7_1940_1_2_64_78	1638	Vran	85.51	11.13	0.01	<0.05
30	ZA7_1940_1_3_70_85	1639	Vran	88.43	11.51	0.04	<0.05
31	ZA7_1940_1_5_30_40	1640	Vran	91.43	11.90	0.01	<0.05
32	ZA7_1940_1_6_25_50	1641	Vran	93.12	12.12	0.00	<0.05
33	ZA7_1940_1_7_90_100	1643	Vran	93.58	12.18	0.01	<0.05
34	ZA4A_1830_4_4_67_75	1575	Nik	86.43	11.25	0.29	<0.05
35	ZA4A_1830_4_4_15_20	1575	Nik	93.89	12.22	0.14	<0.05
36	ZA4A_1830_4_2_60_85	1573	Nik	67.53	8.79	0.44	<0.05
37	ZA3_1883_6_1_80_90	1660	Mys	0.38	0.05	0.28	0.91
38	ZA3_1883_6_2_70_75	1661	Mys	0.54	0.07	0.64	7.59
39	ZA3_1883_6_3_65_75	1662	Mys	0.00	0.00	0.61	2.06
40	ZA3_1883_6_4_85_95	1663	Mys	1.23	0.16	0.36	1.12
41	ZA4A_1988_5_1_40_45	1730	Mys	0.15	0.02	0.13	<0.05
42	ZA4A_1988_5_1_65_70	1730	Mys	0.38	0.05	0.05	<0.05
43	ZA4A_1988_5_3_60_70	1732	Mys	0.08	0.01	1.45	<0.05
44	ZA4A_1988_5_4_85_95	1733	Mys	0.08	0.01	2.72	<0.05
45	ZA4A_1988_5_5_60_70	1734	Mys	0.46	0.06	0.13	<0.05

Table 4-2a. Calcite and dolomite content (Cal, Dol), total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in cuttings samples from ZA3 well ordered by measured depth

No.	Sample No.	ZA3 Depth (m)	Stratigraphy	Calc, Dol (%m)	TIC (%m)	TOC (%m)	TS (%m)
1	2310021	1200	Hus	17.4	2.09	2.01	<0.05
2	2310022	1205	Hus	15.8	1.90	1.74	0.15
3	2310023	1210	Hus	11.7	1.40	2.11	0.23
4	2310024	1215	Hus	16.3	1.96	1.52	0.63
5	2310025	1220	Hus	13.8	1.66	1.80	0.41
6	2310026	1225	Hus	15.9	1.91	1.86	0.25
7	2310027	1230	Hus	15.8	1.90	2.03	0.29
8	2310028	1235	Hus	13.5	1.62	2.26	<0.05
9	2310029	1240	Hus	14.8	1.77	2.06	0.12
10	2310030	1245	Hus	16.0	1.92	2.50	0.16
11	2310031	1250	Hus	15.6	1.87	2.03	0.13
12	2310032	1255	Hus	18.7	2.24	1.78	0.05
13	2310033	1260	Hus	17.3	2.07	1.75	0.09
14	2310034	1265	Hus	12.0	1.44	1.95	0.08
15	2310035	1270	Hus	11.5	1.38	1.69	0.36
16	2310036	1275	Men	33.7	4.04	5.04	3.01
17	2310037	1280	Men	37.5	4.50	1.40	1.41
18	2310038	1285	Men	39.0	4.68	0.99	0.44
19	2310039	1290	Men	33.2	3.98	0.72	0.62
20	2310040	1295	Men	45.7	5.48	0.45	0.49
21	2310041	1300	Nem	12.1	1.45	1.75	1.11
22	2310042	1305	Nem	6.4	0.77	2.02	1.21
23	2310043	1310	Nem	3.7	0.44	2.15	1.27
24	2310044	1315	Nem	5.9	0.71	1.69	1.06
25	2310045	1320	Nem	5.2	0.62	1.44	0.9
26	2310046	1325	Nem	9.6	1.15	1.12	0.9
27	2310047	1330	Nem	25.8	3.09	0.30	0.22
28	2310048	1335	Nem	29.2	3.50	0.36	0.15
29	2310049	1340	Nem	18.8	2.26	0.67	0.51
30	2310050	1345	Nem	11.8	1.41	1.43	1.72

Table 4-2b. Calcite and dolomite content (Cal, Dol), total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in cuttings samples from ZA3 well ordered by measured depth

No.	Sample No.	ZA3 Depth (m)	Stratigraphy	Calc, Dol (%m)	TIC (%m)	TOC (%m)	TS (%m)
31	2310051	1350	Nem	4.1	0.49	1.99	2.57
32	2310052	1355	Nem	6.7	0.80	1.28	1.86
33	2310053	1360	Nem	15.0	1.80	0.43	0.55
34	2310054	1365	Nem	12.6	1.51	0.53	0.28
35	2310055	1370	Nem	17.5	2.10	0.55	0.29
36	2310056	1375	Nem	14.0	1.68	0.43	0.18
37	2310057	1380	Nem	12.8	1.53	0.47	0.22
38	2310058	1385	Nem	28.8	3.46	0.40	0.22
39	2310059	1390	Nem	16.7	2.00	0.69	0.47
40	2310060	1395	Nem	16.3	1.95	0.83	0.37
41	2310061	1400	Nem	21.1	2.53	0.70	0.56
42	2310062	1405	Nem	19.3	2.32	0.79	0.46
43	2310063	1410	Nem	14.4	1.73	1.21	0.75
44	2310064	1415	Nem	12.0	1.44	1.78	1.16
45	2310065	1420	Nem	16.7	2.00	2.60	1.42
46	2310066	1425	Nem	21.3	2.56	2.22	1.13
47	2310067	1430	Nem	12.0	1.44	1.40	0.97
48	2310068	1435	Nem	20.0	2.40	2.71	1.3
49	2310069	1440	Nem	28.3	3.40	1.52	0.95
50	2310070	1445	Nem	26.2	3.14	1.34	0.89
51	2310071	1450	Nem	15.7	1.88	1.59	1.28
52	2310072	1455	Nem	10.7	1.28	1.76	1.32
53	2310073	1457	Nem	14.3	1.71	3.93	1.67
54	2310074	1460	Nes	23.4	2.81	2.35	0.72
55	2310075	1475	Nes	43.3	5.20	5.31	1.05
56	2310076	1480	Nes	39.8	4.77	5.11	1.01
57	2310077	1485	Nes	47.8	5.74	6.76	1.08
58	2310078	1490	Nes	31.3	3.76	3.24	0.78
59	2310079	1495	Nes	24.3	2.91	3.77	1.43
60	2310080	1500	Nes	32.5	3.90	3.28	1.03

Table 4-2c. Calcite and dolomite content (Cal, Dol), total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in cuttings samples from ZA3 well ordered by measured depth

No.	Sample No.	ZA3 Depth (m)	Strati-graphy	Calc, Dol (%m)	TIC (%m)	TOC (%m)	TS (%m)
61	2310081	1505	Nes	41.2	4.94	2.76	1.04
62	2310082	1510	Nes	43.2	5.18	2.58	1.15
63	2310083	1515	Nes	31.4	3.77	2.37	1.65
64	2310084	1520	Nes	36.2	4.34	2.18	1.12
65	2310085	1525	Nes	34.6	4.15	2.38	1.07
66	2310086	1530	Nes	34.2	4.10	2.39	1.07
67	2310087	1535	Nes	34.5	4.14	2.36	1.04
68	2310088	1540	Nes	28.3	3.40	2.08	0.84
69	2310089	1545	Nes	29.6	3.55	2.39	1.07
70	2310090	1550	Nes	33.3	4.00	2.06	1.16
71	2310091	1555	Nes	29.3	3.51	2.43	1.18
72	2310092	1560	Nes	29.3	3.51	2.25	1.32
73	2310093	1565	Nes	21.8	2.62	1.90	1.92
74	2310094	1570	Vran	62.9	8.21	0.65	0.43
75	2310095	1580	Vran	75.5	9.85	0.39	0.39
76	2310096	1585	Vran	82.2	10.72	0.30	0.14
77	2310097	1590	Vran	83.0	10.82	0.20	0.11
78	2310098	1600	Vran	65.9	8.59	0.61	0.34
79	2310099	1605	Vran	79.8	10.41	0.24	0.14
80	2310100	1610	Vran	81.7	10.66	0.28	0.29
81	2310101	1615	Vran	87.8	11.45	0.20	0.23
82	2310102	1620	Vran	89.2	11.63	0.15	0.07
83	2310103	1625	Vran	83.8	10.93	0.24	0.21
84	2310104	1630	Vran	89.5	11.67	0.16	0.12
85	2310105	1635	Vran	87.9	11.47	0.17	<0.05
86	2310106	1640	Vran	76.1	9.93	0.46	0.17
87	2310107	1645	Vran	86.3	11.26	0.25	0.2
88	2310108	1650	Vran	74.8	9.76	0.53	0.14
89	2310109	1655	Vran	89.7	11.70	0.16	<0.05
90	2310110	1660	Vran	88.4	11.53	0.16	<0.05

Table 4-2d. Calcite and dolomite content (Cal, Dol), total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in cuttings samples from ZA3 well ordered by measured depth

No.	Sample No.	ZA3 Depth (m)	Stratigraphy	Calc, Dol (%m)	TIC (%m)	TOC (%m)	TS (%m)
91	2310111	1665	Vran	85.5	11.15	0.22	0.12
92	2310112	1670	Vran	78.6	10.25	0.28	0.22
93	2310113	1675	Vran	77.8	10.15	0.37	0.24
94	2310114	1680	Vran	91.9	11.99	0.09	0.12
95	2310115	1685	Vran	93.5	12.19	0.08	<0.05
96	2310116	1690	Vran	92.3	12.04	<0.05	0.06
97	2310117	1695	Vran	94.3	12.30	0.06	<0.05
98	2310118	1700	Vran	88.5	11.54	0.18	<0.05
99	2310119	1705	Vran	71.6	9.34	0.38	0.19
100	2310120	1710	Vran	89.1	11.62	0.20	<0.05
101	2310121	1720	Vran	86.9	11.34	0.25	<0.05
102	2310122	1722	Vran	88.2	11.50	0.92	<0.05
103	2310123	1723	Vran	86.4	11.27	1.33	<0.05
104	2310124	1725	Vran	87.8	11.45	0.37	0.11
105	2310125	1730	Vran	87.6	11.43	0.39	0.09
106	2310126	1735	Vran	92.6	12.08	0.19	<0.05
107	2310127	1740	Vran	90.2	11.76	0.21	0.09
108	2310128	1741	Vran	90.9	11.86	0.11	0.14
109	2310129	1745	Vran	89.4	11.66	0.19	0.07
110	2310130	1755	Vran	90.9	11.86	0.28	<0.05
111	2310131	1770	Vran	82.0	10.70	0.36	<0.05
112	2310132	1830	Vran	95.1	12.41	0.10	<0.05
113	2310133	1840	Vran	92.7	12.09	0.31	<0.05
114	2310134	1845	Vran	89.3	11.65	0.24	<0.05
115	2310135	1893	Mys	4.1	0.49	34.77	0.92
116	2310136	1900	Mys	38.9	4.67	2.13	0.87
117	2310137	1905	Mys	0.6	0.07	0.75	0.06
118	2310138	1910	Mys	0.0	<0.05	0.95	0.1
119	2310139	1915	Mys	1.2	0.14	2.96	0.11
120	2310140	1920	Mys	0.5	0.06	17.43	0.24
121	2310141	1923	Mys	0.7	0.08	8.00	0.16

Fig. 4-1: Carbonate, i.e. calcite or dolomite content, total organic carbon (TOC) and total sulfur (TS) in respect to true vertical depth (TVD SS) in drilling cuttings in the ZA3 well.

The geochemical profiles in Fig. 4-1 and 4-2 based on carbon and sulfur elemental composition and Rock-Eval pyrolysis show important trends in rock properties. The overthrust **Ždánice-Hustopeče Fm** is built by deep water sediments, low in carbonates, intermediate in TOC, low in sulfur and hydrogen index (HI). **Menilite Fm.** is

exceptional with elevated carbonate minerals (probably marls of the Dynow Fm.), high organic carbon, very high sulfur and the highest HI indicating high source potential due to high algae content and anoxic depositional conditions. **Němčice formation** (third caprock) was deposited in open marine (oceanic) conditions, it has low amount of carbonates, TOC lower but sulfur even higher than that in the Menilite Fm. Thermal maturity of the entire Ždánice overthrust unit is low and did not reach beginning of the oil window.

The **Nesvačilka Fm.** (second caprock) of Eocene age has higher calcareous component, very high TOC and HI typical of redeposited coaly particles with some contribution of marine planktonic algae. No striking change in thermal maturity (T_{max} in Fig. 4-2) is observed at the overthrust – autochthonous Paleogene boundary.

Fig. 4-2: Carbonate mineral (calcite and dolomite) content calculated from total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC), hydrogen index (HI) and thermal maturity index (Tmax) in respect to depth (TVD SS) in ZA3 well profile.

The **main reservoir – Vranovice Fm.** with probable **Nikolčice Fm.** in the lower part is built by dolomites with 4 (or 5) clay enriched horizons in the upper part (Fig. 4-1 and Fig. 4-2). The formation is lean in sedimentary organic carbon. Elevated hydrogen index occurs in the lower part, most probably associated with precipitated solid bitumen from the oil impregnations.

The underlying **Myslejšovice Fm.** of Carboniferous age (underlying seal) has very low carbonate content, probably due to deposition below CCD. Redeposited coaly fragments make the anomalously TOC elevated, HI indicates typical humic type III of kerogen. Thermal maturity is markedly higher than the above part of the profile. This is interpreted as an evidence of deeper burial depth and subsequent erosion of the upper part of Carboniferous strata. That may explain, why the porosity and permeability of the Myslejšovice Fm. is very low.

The reservoir and caprocks of the Zar-3 storage site differ among themselves in carbonate mineral content and total sulfur and form geochemical groups (Fig. 4-3).

Fig. 4-3: Total sulfur content (TS) versus carbonate mineral (calcite and dolomite) content in rocks in Zar-3 storage site calculated from total inorganic carbon (TIC).

While the dolomites of the Vranovice Fm. are very rich in TIC, they are lean in sulfur. Dolomitic sandstones of the Nikolčice Fm. show elevated sulfur content. Nesvačilka Fm. contains a broad range of carbonates and high amount of sulfur, mostly as pyrite. Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. is very lean in carbonates and has a broad range of sulfur content.

4.2 Mineral composition of rocks

Mineral composition was evaluated based on XRD, elemental composition, chemistry by XRF and microscopy. The data are stored in the project repository. Selected samples representing the caprocks and reservoirs were characterised also by wet chemistry method. The data show, the the iron content in dolomites is low, i.e. that the iron rich dolomite does not occur in the Zar-3 storage site. This fact is very important for the fluid-rock interactions modelling and will be discussed later.

Table 4-3: Major carbonate components: total inorganic carbon (TIC), iron (Fe₂O₃ and FeO), magnesium (MgO), manganese (MnO) and calcium oxides (CaO) obtained by wet chemistry methods

No.	Well_MD_c_b_cm1_2	Lithostratigraphy	TIC (%)	Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	FeO (%)	MgO (%)	MnO (%)	CaO (%)
1	UH11_1322_2_4_20_25	Nesvačilka Fm.	3.41	0.51	0.54	0.71	0.010	16.82
2	UH9_1756_1_2_20_30	Nesvačilka Fm.	3.97	< 0.01	0.88	0.69	0.008	21.03
3	ZA3_1460_1_1	Nesvačilka Fm.	2.23	0.60	0.28	5.60	0.018	12.52
4	ZA3_1465,5_2_7_5_15	Nesvačilka Fm.	5.66	< 0.01	0.90	0.95	0.009	31.97
5	ZA3_1465,5_2_9_1	Nesvačilka Fm.	5.48	< 0.01	0.76	0.89	0.007	30.84
6	ZA3_1465,5_2_9_2	Nesvačilka Fm.	4.79	< 0.01	1.02	0.68	0.007	27.20
7	ZA4_1862_1_6_40_55	Nesvačilka Fm.	0.30	0.66	0.37	2.18	0.024	3.60
8	UH-3_1707_3a_3_30_40	Mikulov Fm.	7.80	0.44	0.90	2.80	0.020	36.87
9	UH-3_1707_3a_3_60_70	Mikulov Fm.	8.12	0.29	1.06	2.88	0.020	36.31
10	ZA3_1701_4_2_85_95	Vranovice Fm.	12.30	< 0.01	0.31	14.57	0.064	32.95
11	ZA4A_1759_1_3_15_25	Vranovice Fm.	12.08	< 0.01	0.30	14.88	0.053	32.81
12	ZA4A_1778_2_4_35_45	Vranovice Fm.	12.15	< 0.01	0.29	14.50	0.050	33.37
13	ZA4A_1787_3_1_20_30	Vranovice Fm.	12.31	< 0.01	0.28	12.46	0.057	31.68
14	ZA7_1940_1_2_64_78	Vranovice Fm.	11.13	< 0.01	0.55	17.80	0.061	29.86
15	ZA7_1940_1_5_30_40	Vranovice Fm.	11.90	< 0.01	0.48	17.60	0.054	30.84
16	UH9_1911_2B_1_40_50	Myslejovice Fm.	<0.05	1.29	2.70	1.79	0.041	0.29

Vranovice Fm., the principal reservoir, represents an end member lithology of almost pure dolomite (Fig. 4-4). The Nikolčice Fm., which underlies the Vranovice Fm., is rich in dolomite but has also quartz and minor rock-building minerals, such as feldspars.

Simplified review of calculated calcite, dolomite and clay minerals + quartz + feldspars content for the reservoir and caprocks is in Tab. 4-4 to 4-6 and Fig. 4-4.

Table 4-4: Calculated calcite, dolomite and clay minerals + quartz (Q) + feldspars (F) content for the caprocks of the Nesvačilka and Mikulov Fms.

No.	Sample Name (well_MD_C_B_from_to)	TVD SS (m)	Chrono- stratig.	Lithostratigraphy	seal/ reservoir	Clay+Q+F	Calcite%	Dol%	Control sum
1	UH11_1322_2_4_20_25	1074	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	50.6	49.4	0.0	100.0
2	ZA3_1460_1_1_35_45	1237	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	seal	53.3	1.6	45.1	100.0
3	ZA3_1460_1_1	1237	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	43.5	8.1	48.4	100.0
4	ZA3_1460_1_3_95_97	1240	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	68.5	31.0	0.5	100.0
5	ZA3_1460_1_4_67_73	1240	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	94.3	5.1	0.6	100.0
6	ZA3_1465,5_2_1_45_48	1243	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
7	ZA3_1460_1_4_67_73	1241	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	seal	96.8	3.2	0.0	100.0
8	ZA3_1465,5_2_1_45_48	1243	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	89.8	4.9	5.4	100.0
9	ZA3_1465,5_2_7	1248	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	37.6	62.4	0.0	100.0
10	ZA3_1465,5_2_7_20_30	1248	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	seal	35.1	63.8	1.1	100.0
11	ZA3_1465,5_2_9_1	1250	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	39.2	60.8	0.0	100.0
12	ZA3_1465,5_2_9_2	1250	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	45.7	54.3	0.0	100.0
13	ZA1_1700_22_4_45_55	1477	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	57.5	41.4	1.1	100.0
14	ZA1_1740_24_5_60_70	1519	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	65.4	34.4	0.2	100.0
15	UH9_1756_1_2_20_30	1535	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	52.1	47.9	0.0	100.0
16	ZA4_1862_1_5_51_72	1573	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	seal	80.7	0.3	19.0	100.0
17	ZA4_1862_1_6	1574	M. Pg	Zarosice Mb.	seal	83.7	0.7	15.7	100.0
18	ZA4_1862_1_6_80_90	1574	M. Pg	Žarošice Mb.	seal	90.1	0.0	9.9	100.0
19	UH3_1707_3a_3_30_40	1418	U. Jur	Mikulov Fm.	seal	18.1	62.1	19.8	100.0
20	UH3_1707_3a_3_60_70	1418	U. Jur	Mikulov Fm.	seal	59.1	0.0	40.9	100.0
21	UH-3_1707_3a_3_60_70	1418	U. Jur	Mikulov Fm.	Seal	18.1	64.0	0.0	82.0
22	ZA5H_2093_1_3_45_55	1468	U. Jur	Mikulov Fm.	seal	1.2	96.9	2.0	100.0
23	ZA5H_2093_1_1_5_15	1464	U. Jur	Mikulov Fm.	seal	1.5	95.7	2.7	100.0

Table 4-5: Calculated calcite, dolomite and clay minerals + quartz (Q) + feldspars (F) content for Jurassic reservoirs of Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms.

No	Sample Name (well MD_C_B from_to)	TVD SS (m)	Chrono- strat	Lithostratigraphy	seal / reservoir	Clay+Q+F	Calcite%	Dol%	Contr ol sum
24	UH-3_1973_7_2_90_95	1683	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.9	0.0	99.2	100.0
25	ZA3_1595,5_3_4_51_61	1375	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.9	0.0	99.2	100.0
26	ZA3_1595,5_3_4_80_90	1376	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.9	0.0	99.2	100.0
27	ZA3_1701_4_2_85_95	1479	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	1.6	0.0	98.4	100.0
28	ZA4A_1759_1_3_15_25	1502	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0
29	ZA4A_1778_2_4_35_45	1523	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.2	0.0	99.8	100.0
30	ZA4A_1778_2_8_50_55	1527	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.9	0.0	99.1	100.0
31	ZA4A_1787_3_1_20_30	1528	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	1.2	0.0	98.8	100.0
32	ZA4A_1787_3_3_25_30	1530	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.5	0.0	99.5	100.0
33	ZA4A_1787_3_8_45_55	1536	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0
34	ZA6A_1929_1_3_80_90	1565	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	2.2	0.0	97.8	100.0
35	ZA7_1940_1_2_64_78	1637	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.6	0.0	99.4	100.0
36	ZA7_1940_1_5_30_40	1640	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0
37	ZA7_1940_1_6_25_50	1641	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.3	0.0	99.7	100.0
38	ZA7_1940_1_7_90_100	1642	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.7	0.0	99.3	100.0
39	ZA3_1785_5_1_60_70	1561	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.1	0.0	99.9	100.0
40	ZA4A_1778_2_8_45_55	1527	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	0.1	0.0	99.9	100.0
41	ZA7_1940_1_3_70_85	1638	U. Jur	Vranovice Fm.	res	1.8	0.0	98.2	100.0
42	ZA4A_1830_4_4_67_75	1574	U. Jur	Vran./Nikol. Fm.	res	4.5	0.2	95.3	100.0
43	ZA4A_1830_4_2_60_85	1573	M. Jur	Nikolčice Fm.	res	42.2	0.0	57.8	100.0
44	ZA4A_1830_4_4_15_20	1574	U. Jur	Vran./Nikol. Fm.	res	0.9	0.0	99.1	100.0

Table 4-6: Calculated calcite, dolomite and clay minerals + quartz (Q) + feldspars (F) content for the underlying Carboniferous caprocks (Myslejovice Fm.)

No.	Sample Name (well_MD_C_B_from_to)	TVD SS (m)	Chrono- strati- graphy	Lithostratigraphy	seal/ reservoir	Clay+Q+F	Calcite%	Dol%	Control sum
45	ZA3_1883_6_1_80_90	1659	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
46	ZA3_1883_6_2_70_75	1660	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	96.9	3.1	0.0	100.0
47	ZA3_1883_6_3_65_75	1661	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	98.9	0.0	1.1	100.0
48	ZA3_1883_6_3_65_75	1662	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	98.7	0.0	1.3	100.0
49	UH9_1756_2B_1_40_50	1688	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
50	ZA4A_1988_5_1_65_70	1729	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
51	ZA4A_1988_5_1_40_45	1729	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
52	ZA4A_1988_5_3_60_70	1732	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	Seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
53	ZA4A_1988_5_4_85_95	1733	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
54	ZA4A_1988_5_5_60_70	1733	L. Car	Myslejovice Fm.	seal	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0

Overlying caprocks are built by marls of the **Mikulov Fm.**, which show broad variety of mineral composition, little or no dolomite, abundant calcite, siliciclastics, mainly clay minerals, and pyrite.

Second caprocks built by Paleogene siltstones of the **Nesvačilka Fm.** are rich in quartz, feldspars, clays, pyrite and have variable amount of calcite. The pre-experimental results were used, among others, for optimization of the experimental conditions of the fluid – rock interactions (Task 5.4, report R5.5).

Fig. 4-4: Ternary plot of dolomite, calcite, and chlorite + quartz + feldspar (Cl+Q+Fsp) of rock samples from the selected lithostratigraphic units of the Zar-3 storage complex: Paleogene (Pg) of the Žarošice Mb., Upper Jurassic (J3) of the Mikulov, Vranovice, and Nikolčice Formations., Lower Carboniferous (C1) of the Myslejovice Fm. The numbers in legend indicate 1 – lower, 3 – upper chronostratigraphic unit. Data points for the caprocks are included.

The underlying Carboniferous **Myslejovice Fm.** is built by almost pure siliciclastic rocks (shale, siltstone and sandstone), which consist of quartz, feldspars and clay minerals.

4.3 Optical and electron microscopy

Reservoir and caprock characteristics were complemented by microscopy in translucent and fluorescent light. Detailed descriptions and photomicrographs are in the Petrographic atlas of reservoirs and caprocks (Attachement 2 a 3 to this report).

Reservoir samples are represented by Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm. rocks. **Vranovice Fm.** consists of **dolostones** with fine to coarse grain size, rarely also **oolitic limestones**. **Nikolčice Fm.** is represented mainly by **sandy dolostones**.

Oolitic limestones (Fig. 4-5) are present in the upper part of the **Vranovice Fms.** The rock can be characterized as oolitic packstone to grainstone with pellets. Micrite is partly recrystallized to dolomitic sparite, or leached. Newly formed pyrite is quite abundant in the sample. Ooide envelopes are developed in three types: a) dark concentric, b) micritic lacking texture and c) light radial. Ooid centers are sometimes leached or recrystallized. Rarely, relics of fossils can be found in ooid centers. The facies can be assigned to shelf lagoon with open circulation, moderate to low energy conditions. Limestone is affected by compaction and pressure dissolution resulting in stylolites. Whole oolitic limestone has orange fluorescence, most probably due to oil nano-inclusions.

Fig. 4-5: Concentric and radial envelopes of Vranovice Fm. ooides in PPL (left) showing warm orange UV fluorescence caused by bituminous nano-inclusions (right).

Majority of **Vranovice Fm.** consists of dolostones that have undergone multiple stages of dissolution (**karstification**), dolomitization, collapsing causing **brecciation** and dolomite cementation. This can be demonstrated on medium-grained dolomite breccias, which are fully dolomitized and have collapsed rock texture. This process happened at very shallow marine conditions with periodical emerging and submerging below the sea level. The resulting highly **vuggy porosity** (cavernous and not interconnected) formed during secondary stage of dolomite dissolution (Fig. 4-6 to 4-9). With increasing depth, the dolostone breccias tend to be more compacted and less porous.

Fig. 4-6: left and right: Vranovice Fm. brecciated dolostones have undergone multiple processes, including dolomitization, dissolution, karstification, brecciation (colaps) and another stage of dissolution, forming vuggy porosity.

Fig. 4-7: Planar-s dolomite in Vranovice Fm. lining the pore partly filled by dolomicrite (PPL, left) has outer non fluorescent rim (right).

Fig. 4-8: Light dolomite crystals (PPL, left) show strong fluorescence zonality with dark dolomite rim (right) and bight core with micro-fluid inclusions.

Fig. 4-9: Heavily brecciated dolostone in the Vranovice Fm. cemented by fine grain dolomite and residual bitumens in PPL – plain polarized light (left) and fluorescent light (right).

Microprobe analysis (electron microscopy) reveals presence of nanoporosity in anhedral to euhedral dolomite crystals with Mg:Ca ratio of 0.75-0.91 (Fig. 4-10). This type of pores do not communicate directly with one another.

Fig. 4-10: Left – Vranovice Fm., microporous dolomite with zonal rims. Right - large zonal dolomite crystals in the Nikolčice Fm. between quartz and silicate grains in dolomitic sandstone (NIK1A_1911 m) in microprobe back-scattered electron (BSE) images.

The zonality of dolomite crystals clearly visible in fluorescent light was not sufficiently documented by microprobe. The Mn and Fe contents, which is referred to in literature as the key control in dolomite zonation, was very close to the detection limit of the microprobe instrument. Correlations Ca, Mg and Mn contents are weak, while stronger correlation is observed between Mn and Fe contents in the Vranovice and Nikolčice Fm., where Mn:Fe ratio is 1:5 (Fig. 4-11). In some of the dolomite crystals, relics of original calcite grains are visible.

Fig. 4-11: Ternary plot of chemical compositions of Vranovice and Nikolčice Fm. dolomites.

Caprock microscopy

Layered silty sandstones to arkoses of Carboniferous **Myslejovice Fm.** act as **bottom seal in Zar-3 storage complex**. The rock is composed of subangular grains of quartz, feldspar and rarely mica. The rock is affected by compaction (fitted and sutured contacts of grains). Feldspars are intensely altered to clay minerals or dissolved (Fig. 4-12 left), forming modest interparticle porosity. Small compressed and elongated coal particles were observed in some sandstones. Fracture porosity is developed along stylolites. Rarely, bituminous matter impregnation was found in thin sections, exhibiting warm orange UV fluorescence (Fig. 4-12 right).

Fig. 4-12: Interparticle porosity after feldspar alteration (left, filled by blue epoxy) and orange fluorescence of rarely-occurring oil between grains (right).

First seal partly overlying the Vranovice Fm. reservoir is **Mikulov Fm.** Petrologically, the Mikulov Fm. rocks range from **marly wackestones** to (silty) carbonatic/dolomitic sandstones (Falkenstein Fm. in Austria). Overall the rocks are fine grained (Fig. 4-13), with high amount of clay, subangular bioclastic detritus and (sub)rounded intraclasts and pellets. Alochems are partly leached and recrystallized, forming minor moldic porosity. The rock is composed of illite-smectite and chlorite-smectite clay and calcitic silt. The rocks are not strongly dissolved (as Vranovice Fm.), but mild fracture porosity occurs. Coarse grained beds are rich in subangular quartz grains. The rock matrix is filled with anhedral dolomite crystals (possible result of original micrite recrystallization). Bituminous matter was scarcely recorded in fracture pores. Kerogen is of planktonic algal origin (type II with alginite or lamalginite).

Fig 4-13: Fine grained marly wackestones of Mikulov Fm. (left) are full of bioclasts (right).

Second seal covering both Vranovice Fm. and Mikulov Fm. is represented by **Nesvačilka Fm. – Žarošice Mb.** silty siltstones, often dolomitic (Fig 4-14). Upper sandstones are heterogeneous, in grain composition and size, ranging from tens of microns up to several mm. Besides quartz, feldspars are present together with fossils and rare glauconite. The siltstone/sandstone is well cemented with isopachous dolomite cement (45 % of the whole rock is represented by dolomite), so only non-communicating intergranular porosity remains. Underlying beds of Nesvačilka Fm. are quite fine grained (below 200 μm ; Fig 4-15), containing mainly quartz and feldspars. Quartz grains are often cracked, while feldspars are altered. Pore space is filled by clay, silt and rarely carbonate cement. Large coal particles up to several cm in size were found in some core samples.

Fig 4-14: Dolomitic sandy siltstone of the Nesvačilka Fm. (left) is cemented by isopachous dolomite cement with remains of interparticle porosity (right).

Fig. 4-15: Sandy siltstone, Nesvačilka Fm. abundant oil impregnation (orange fluorescence) ZA4, TVDSS 1573 m.

Optical porosity

Reservoir and caprocks samples impregnated by blue epoxy resin were analysed using image analysis (Figs. 4-16 and 4-17). The relative area of open pores in a selected thin section area corresponds to optical porosity. The interpreted pore size distributions suggest, that in all rock types the microporosity prevails. In **reservoir** samples (Vranovice Fm.) an important contribution to the reservoir total porosity of cavernous and fracture pores with diameter ranging from 100 to 300 μm exists (Fig. 4-18). The **caprocks** have about 5-10 times lower porosity than the reservoir rocks and have the majority of pores in the clay size microporosity (<5 μm) diameter. More details are included in the Petrographic atlas (Attachement 1 and 2).

Fig. 4-16: Scanned whole thin section pictures of dolomite samples of the Vranovice Fm. Red line delineates the rock impregnated by blue epoxy resin. In the lower row of pictures the separated blue pore areas using image analysis are shown in black as wugs, fractures and pore (dis)connections.

Fig. 4-17: Scanned whole thin section pictures of laminated arkose/siltstone and sandstone of the turbiditic Myslejovice Fm. and siltstone of the Žarošice Fm. Red line delineates the rock impregnated by blue epoxy resin. In the lower row of pictures the separated blue pore areas are shown in black using image analysis and calculated porosity as a ratio of blue area/ total area (%).

Fig. 4-18: Distribution of cumulative and incremental optical porosity as a function of pore size in reservoir rock (Vranovice Fm.) and caprocks (Mikulov and Nesvačilka Fms.).

4.4 Bitumens in reservoir and caprocks and their correlation with reservoir oils

Extractable organic matter in rocks (bitumens) was analysed for biomarkers by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Selected parameters were evaluated evidencing the type of biological origin, depositional environment and thermal maturity (Francu et al. 1996; Picha and Peters 1998, Picha et al. 2006). The same data were analysed in all sedimentary formations and oils in Zar-3 storage complex and broader vicinity. Mutual comparison is made of rocks and fluids and conclusions are drawn on fluid migration in the eastern Bohemian Massif below the West Carpathians.

The principal biomarker groups include triterpanes (hopanes), steranes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their alkylated homologues (phenanthrenes). At shallow depth the biomarker parameters reflect the biological configuration. With increasing depth and temperature the molecules change to more geological form. The diagenetic and catagenetic trends of the source rocks are shown in Figs. 4-19 and 4-20 based on the core samples from deep wells affected by oil migration as well as those not affected. The Jurassic source rocks of the Mikulov Fm. show very similar trend of thermal maturation to that of the Paleogene (Těšany and Nesvačilka Fms.). The $22S/(S+R)$ C_{31} hopane ratio and $20S/(S+R)$ C_{29} sterane ratio start at 0.5-1.3 values in the thermally immature interval and reach the oil generation window with values of 0.5-0.6 (hopanes) and 0.45-0.55 (steranes). In the same diagrams oil samples are shown with hopane values of 0.57-0.58 and sterane values of 0.45-0.65 (Fig. 4-19).

Fig. 4-19: $22S/(S+R)$ C_{31} hopane ratio and $20S/(S+R)$ C_{29} sterane ratio in Jurassic (blue squares) and Paleogene rocks (orange crosses) and oils (green circles).

Fig. 4-20: Calculated equivalent vitrinite reflectance (Rc-MPI2) based on methylphenanthrene index in Jurassic (Mikulov, Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms.) and Paleogene rocks (Nesvačilka Fm.) and oils from Zar-3 site and broader vicinity.

Thermal maturity is also measured by the methylphenanthrene index MPI2 (Fig. 4-20), where the Jurassic and Paleogene source rocks show parallel trends with depth, the Jurassic being slightly deeper. The general conclusion based on Figs. 4-19 and 4-20 is that all the source rocks unaffected by migrating oils are markedly less mature than the oils down to depth of 4 km. They become similar at 4-5 km and more. Paleogene caprock samples (but not all of them) in Zar-3 are **impregnated (stained) by migrated oil**, while the unaffected rocks, which occur further away from Zar-3, are of contrastingly lower maturity. Oil impregnations in caprocks are trapped in micropores and can move only by diffusion mechanism within million years.

Multivariate statistics was applied to visualise the **correlation of rock bitumens and oils** in the broader Zar-3 area. Principal component analysis (PCA) and cluster analysis using 10 biomarker ratios sensitive to depositional environment in 60 rock and 26 oil samples are shown in Figs. 4-21 and 4-22. Vectors in Fig. 4-21 point to the direction, in which each biomarker parameter moves the datapoints. The samples form 3 major genetic groups:

Group 1 includes all oils, all reservoir samples in Zar-3 and deeper Jurassic source rocks (Mikulov Fm.).

Group 2 represents Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. away from migration pathways (Kar-1). It does not correlate with any of the oils.

Group 3 includes Paleogene, Jurassic and Carboniferous rocks (Myslejovice Fm.), which also do not correlate with any of the oils.

Fig. 4-21: Principal component analysis (PCA) of 10 biomarker ratios sensitive to depositional environment in 60 rock and 26 oil samples.

The interpretation is that oil and gas generation and regional oil and gas migration in the eastern margin of the Bohemian Massif have occurred since Middle Miocene, i.e. past 16 Ma. Migration took place at least 4-6 km vertically and 15-20 km horizontally below the West Carpathian fold-and-thrust belt. In this context it is not surprising that majority of the sedimentary formations of the Zar-3 storage complex were exposed to migrating fluids. Oil & gas accumulation formed in the dolomite reservoir of the Vranovice Fm. in the Zar-3 structure. Overlying Mikulov Fm. has acted up to now as an efficient caprock. Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. is partly impregnated by bitumens genetically related the reservoir oil but the impregnations are diffusive in their nature and the bitumens are trapped in micropores. The overlying thrust plane of the Ždánice unit together with the shaly Nĕmčice and Menilite Fms. (lower parts of the thrust sheets) act as efficient seal and seal even the Nesvačilka Fm. as a good caprock.

Fig. 4-22: Cluster analysis of 10 biomarker ratios sensitive to depositional environment in 60 rock and 26 oil samples. Major oil family correlates with all reservoir samples and some Paleogene rocks, which are in close contact with the oil reservoir.

Organic geochemical, Rock-Eval pyrolysis and microscopic data were integrated with the Mudlog data and the genetic relationships and impregnation intensity is shown in Fig. 4-23.

Fig. 4-23: Mudlog with indications while drilling of free hydrocarbons in cuttings (horizontal red columns show direct liminiscence under UV, blue columns show enhanced liminiscence after adding chloroform). Size of circles shows abundance of free hydrocarbons in cuttings and core samples.

5 CONCLUSIONS

1. Principal reservoir in the Zar-3 storage complex is brecciated dolomite of the Vranovice Fm. with fracture and vuggy (cavernous) porosity. The dolomitization took place near to sea level in the early phase after limestone deposition. Additional reservoir, Nikolčice Fm., occurs below the Vranovice Fm. It is formed by quartz-dolomitic sandstone deposited in shallow sea.
2. Based on detailed petrography and geochemistry, the original limestone of the Vranovice Fm. formed most probably as a pinnacle reef, which periodically emerged from and submerged below the sea level. These conditions resulted in dolomitization. During emergence, carstification occurred followed by collapses and brecciations.
3. Later, the reef with originally steep walls was drowned and at increased water depth marls of the Mikulov Fm. onlaped on the Vranovice Fm. Facial interfingering probably accompanied the deposition in the Upper Jurassic (Oxfordian). This caprock has very little or no dolomite, calcite is the major mineral constituent.
4. During the Cretaceous and Lower Paleogene, deep submarine canyons were incised into Jurassic formations and created even steeper walls of the earlier reef of the Vranovice Fm. Part of the Mikulov Fm. (caprock) was also removed in the western part of the Zar-3 structure.
5. In the Eocene, sandy and shaly siltstones of the Těšany (not present in the Zar-3) and Nesvačilka Fms. (in Zar-3) were deposited in the canyons often bordered by steep walls of the Jurassic. These rock have variable carbonate content and are enriched in sulfur minerals.
6. In Lower-to-Middle Miocene, the West Carpathian units were thrust on and buried the eastern margin of the Bohemian Massif to depth. As a result, Jurassic source rocks were exposed to increased temperature and oil and gas generation took place. Oil window was documented at depth of 4-6 km and gas generation at 6-9 km.
7. Since that time, regional migration of oil and gas occurred and all the formations in Zar-3 storage site were exposed to migrating hydrocarbons.
8. More than 100 m thick oil column and additional 100 m of gas column accumulated in the Zar-3 reservoir of the Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms. This is a convincing evidence, that the Zar-3 structure has been efficiently sealed.
9. Caprocks show 5-10 (or more) times lower optical porosity than reservoir rocks. Microporosity is dominant in all caprocks.
10. Bitumen (oily) impregnations are observed everywhere in the reservoir and partly also in the Nesvačilka Fm. based on mudlogs, fluorescent microscopy and biomarkers. Both in Mikulov Fm. and in the Ždánice overthrust unit bitumen impregnations are very low or absent.
11. The general conclusion is, that the Zar-3 storage complex is efficiently sealed and will be a safe storage site.

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ATTACHMENTS

Attachment 1: List of core and cuttings samples used for the analyses.

Attachment 2: Petrographic atlas of the reservoir rocks

Attachment 3: Petrographic atlas of the caprocks

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